

An Investigation on Learning Strategies for a Physics-Informed LSTM Model with a Point-Reactor Kinetics Problem

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ABSTRACT

Physics-informed machine learning (PIML) is a hybrid data-physics driven technique that has the potential to increase accuracy, generalization, and explainability of machine learning applications. To demonstrate the benefit of PIML, physics loss was incorporated within a long short-term memory (LSTM) model to solve the point reactor kinetics response of a fast neutron system. Compared to a traditional LSTM, the physics-informed LSTM exhibited much greater accuracy in extrapolated conditions, demonstrating a greater ability to generalize given the same training. The physics-informed LSTM was also able to significantly outperform a physics-informed neural network architecture. Further, to better manage the optimization of multiple loss terms associated with the physics-informed LSTM model, several learning algorithms, including *SoftAdapt*, *ReLoBRaLo*, *Learning Rate Annealing*, and *GradNorm*, were applied to the subject problem. With each learning strategy a high degree of performance was achieved, namely: R^2 coefficients > 0.99 and RMSE values $< 1\%$. This work provides a foundation for future investigation of the applications of loss balancing, including mitigating the effects of inaccurate or uncertain physics parameters and physics equations, accelerating anomaly detection, and adapting prior physics parameter estimates to best fit operational data.

Keywords: Physics-Informed Machine Learning, Point Reactor Kinetics, Learning Strategy, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

Physics-informed machine learning (PIML) [1] aims at improving SciML models' accuracy, generalization, and data efficiency by integrating physical laws and domain knowledge into the training process. The most popular PIML technique is physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) [2], which add the physics equations as a constraint within the neural network's loss function to enable a physics-constrained learning process, making them more efficient and accurate than purely data-driven networks. In the context of nuclear reactor physics modeling & simulation, PINNs have been used to predict the dynamic reactor responses to changes in reactivity, power, and temperature through the point-reactor kinetics (PRK) equations [3].

The use of PINNs in the realms of reactor dynamics and other nuclear engineering applications is increasing in popularity, partially due to their low run time after training, their data-driven predictions, and their potential resilience to incomplete physics. However, existing issues in PINN training must be addressed to further increase confidence in their predictions. An especially relevant issue is the unbalanced back-propagated gradients during training [4]. PINNs are constructed by adding multiple loss terms from balance equations, data, and initial/boundary conditions to the loss function. When optimizing the total loss function during the training process, if not properly weighted, certain terms may dominate depending on the scale of the loss term. This issue has been demonstrated to adversely

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impact the performance of PINNs [4]. Furthermore, balancing of loss terms may also allow for better adaptability to incorrect physics, e.g. uncertain PRK parameters, or unknown temperature feedback mechanisms, by favoring data-loss after returns from reducing physics-loss diminish. A data-driven approach to addressing incomplete physics is a particular advantage of SciML methods over traditional ODE and PDE solvers.

This work seeks to investigate potential learning strategies to balance physics and data-driven losses to accelerate learning, increase accuracy, provide additional resilience against incomplete physics, and maintain generalization capabilities provided by physics-informed techniques. A traditional PINN using fully-connected linear layers, a long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network, and a physics-informed LSTM (PI-LSTM) are investigated. Then, various learning strategies are applied to the PI-LSTM architecture, including *SoftAdapt* [5], *Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback* (ReLoBRaLo) [6], *Learning Rate Annealing* (LRA) [4], and *GradNorm* [7] are investigated. Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is performed using Monte Carlo dropout (MCD) to evaluate the reliability of predictions.

The following study aims to contribute to reactor operations research by creating a framework for predicting full reactor operations that contain multiple transients and reactivity perturbations. While a traditional PINN architecture is found to be suitable in predicting single transients [3], the results from this work find a PI-LSTM to be a more suitable architecture for predicting many different full operations. Additionally, this study uses reactor dynamics through the PRK equations as a benchmark for applying various loss balancing strategies to improve the performance of the PI-LSTM. These loss-balancing strategies are solely applied to the PI-LSTM model as the PI-LSTM architecture is found to greatly outperform the PINN model in predicting multiple time-dependent operations.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the subject problem, model architecture, and PINN learning strategies used. Section 3 discusses the performance of each proposed model architecture and the PI-LSTM's performance using each of the proposed learning strategies. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2. METHODOLOGIES

2.1. The Point-Reactor Kinetics Problem

The problem used as a case study in this work is the response of a Godiva-like system to small, short reactivity insertions. The simplified six-group PRK model is based on Serpent [8] simulations of the Godiva critical experiment. A sample operation consists of two random supercritical states over the course of 5 seconds. Supercritical states were uniformly sampled between 5 and 100 pcm and between 0.5 and 2.0 seconds in duration. The training, validation, and testing sets consist of 1267, 148, and 74 data points, respectively, obtained by numerically solving the PRK equations for each operation. An additional dataset with an expanded feature range of 3 transients of 5-120 pcm and 0.5-3.0 seconds each was generated to test the generalization capabilities of the LSTM and PIML models. The governing equations for the PRK model are:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \frac{\rho - \beta}{\Lambda} n(t) + \sum_{d=1}^6 \lambda_d C_d(t) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dC_d}{dt} = \frac{\beta_d}{\Lambda} n(t) - \lambda_d C_d(t), \quad d = 1, 2, \dots, 6, \quad (1)$$

Where the neutron and precursor populations, $n(t)$ and $C_d(t)$, are determined using the reactivity, ρ and the PRK physics parameters, Λ , λ_d , β , and β_d .

2.2. Model Architecture

Three ML models are studied in this work: conventional PINN, LSTM, and PI-LSTM. LSTMs are particularly suited for predicting time series data (such as reactor transients) by maintaining a memory of

short-term patterns (the hidden state) and long-term patterns (the cell state) within the data [9]. The PINN, LSTM, and PI-LSTM architectures are all investigated to determine which is most suited for predicting reactor operations.

The LSTM and PI-LSTM models are constructed using two LSTM layers consisting of 50 units each with a hyperbolic tangent activation function and a linear output layer. The LSTM layers are simply replaced with linear layers that use a ReLU activation function for the PINN model. Dropout layers are placed between each weighted layer for regularization and uniform uncertainty sampling when performing UQ using MCD. All three models use the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01.

The data loss term \mathcal{L}_D is calculated using the mean absolute error (MAE), and is used as the total loss term for the LSTM. The loss function of the PI models consists of two additional components: the physics loss (\mathcal{L}_P) and initial condition loss (\mathcal{L}_{IC}). \mathcal{L}_{IC} is calculated as the MAE from the initial condition for the neutron population $n(0)$ and the delayed neutron precursor concentrations for each energy group $C_d(0)$:

$$n(0) = n_o \quad \text{and} \quad C_d(0) = n_o \frac{\beta_d}{\lambda_d \Lambda}. \quad (2)$$

The physics-loss, \mathcal{L}_P , is calculated using a conservation term derived from Equation (1):

$$\mathcal{L}_P = \frac{1}{MK} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^K \left| \frac{\rho_{k,m} - \beta}{\Lambda} n_{k,m}(t) - \frac{dn_{k,m}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_{k,m,i}(t) \right|, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{L}_P is summed over M individual reactor operations consisting of K time points. The PINN and PI-LSTM models weigh the data, initial condition, and PRK losses initially by 0.3, 0.4, and 0.3, respectively. The model architecture described for the PI-LSTM is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PI-LSTM architecture

2.3. Learning Strategies

When training a PINN, the total loss term, \mathcal{L} , may be decomposed into a loss term for each task (i.e., physics, data, ICs), \mathcal{L}_i , and an associated scaling weight for each loss term, λ_i . The total loss term is then expressed as a summation of the losses with respect to the model's parameters, θ , and weights across k terms,

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i(t). \quad (4)$$

When optimizing the total loss function, each of these terms are competing interests, where one term may dominate depending on the scale of the loss term. This issue has been found to be one of the most prominent in PINN training, leading to losses in accuracy and decreased confidence in PINN usage. The following sections discuss several learning strategies used to optimize the scaling weights λ_i for each objective to ensure balanced training.

Each of the proposed strategies is found to introduce new hyperparameters that may be tuned to ensure predictive accuracy. To ensure a fair comparison of each method, with minimal influence of hyperparameter value, Bayesian hyperparameter optimization of the newly introduced hyperparameters is performed.

2.3.1. SoftAdapt

SoftAdapt is an algorithm for balancing multiple loss terms introduced in [5]. The algorithm applies weights to individual parts of the overall loss function following

$$\lambda_i = \frac{e^{\beta(s_i - \max(s_j))}}{\sum_{j=1}^m e^{\beta(s_j - \max(s_j))}} \quad \text{and} \quad s_i = \mathcal{L}_i(t) - \mathcal{L}_i(t-1), \quad (5)$$

where β is a hyperparameter controlling the “softness” of each term, similar to the SoftMax activation function, as $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ the function approaches a hard maximum, and a $\beta < 0$ prioritizes the best performing losses. The value s is the change in the loss component over the course of a training step. The SoftAdapt algorithm biases the training towards reducing the loss term with the greatest or lowest rate of change, depending on the sign of β . Additional variants of the SoftAdapt algorithm are described by [5]; only the ordinary variant is implemented in this work. For the following study β is tuned within the range $\beta \in [-10, 10]$.

2.3.2. Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback

ReLoBRaLo concerns the continuous updating of k loss weights, λ_i , using loss terms from the previous timestep ($t-1$) and occasionally using the initial loss at $t=0$ to inform the model’s improvement since the beginning of the training process [6]. The total process that ReLoBRaLo takes to update each λ_i is mathematically expressed by:

$$\lambda_i(t) = \alpha \lambda_i^{\text{hist}} + (1 - \alpha) \lambda_i^{\text{bal}}(t, t-1) \quad (6a)$$

where

$$\lambda_i^{\text{bal}}(t, t') = k \cdot \frac{\exp(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i(t)}{\mathcal{T} \mathcal{L}_i(t')})}{\sum_{j=1}^k \exp(\frac{\mathcal{L}_j(t)}{\mathcal{T} \mathcal{L}_j(t')})} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_i^{\text{hist}}(t) = \rho \lambda_i(t-1) + (1 - \rho) \lambda_i^{\text{bal}}(t, 0). \quad (6b)$$

The strategy introduces three new hyperparameters: a “temperature” \mathcal{T} for the SoftAdapt function, an exponential decay rate, α , to smooth λ_i updates, and a Bernoulli random variable, ρ where $\mathbb{E}[\rho] \approx 1$, to allow for an occasional lookback at the initial loss. $\lambda_i^{\text{bal}}(t, t')$ concerns the re-balancing of losses in a similar manner to the SoftAdapt algorithm, hardened by $1/\mathcal{T}$ and normalized by some reference loss at step t' . λ_i^{hist} creates a randomly weighted look-back according to the Bernoulli random variable ρ , incorporating the previous loss weight and the balanced weight with respect to the initial training step. Finally, the loss weights are incorporated using the current λ_i^{hist} and the last steps $\lambda_i^{\text{bal}}(t, t-1)$. The

hyperparameters are optimized within the following ranges according to results of a hyperparameter sensitivity study by [6]: $\mathcal{T} \in [1 \times 10^{-5}, 1.0]$, $\mathbb{E}[\rho] \in [0.99, 0.9999]$, and $\alpha \in [0.9, 0.999]$.

2.3.3. Learning Rate Annealing

LRA is another training strategy proposed by [4] to balance the gradient of each loss term during back-propagation. The algorithm initially defines a decomposition of the total loss term, $\mathcal{L}(\theta)$, into

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) := \mathcal{L}_r(\theta) + \sum_{i=1}^M \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i(\theta), \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_r(\theta)$ represents the physics loss term, while M represents the remaining objectives. The parameter λ_i is dynamically updated during training to balance the gradients of the respective M loss objectives, according to

$$\lambda_i(t) = (1 - \alpha)\lambda_i(t-1) + \alpha \hat{\lambda}_i(t) \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\lambda}_i(t) = \frac{\max_{\theta} \{|\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_r(\theta, t)|\}}{|\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_i(\theta, t)|}, \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\lambda}_i$ is calculated during each mini-batch iteration and is used to balance the loss terms by performing a ratio of the gradient of $\mathcal{L}_r(\theta)$ and the mean of the remaining loss gradients. By this ratio in conjunction with the loss definition in Equation (7), the gradient of each respective loss function inversely affects its static weight. The weight for the next training step, $\lambda_i(t)$ is updated using an exponential moving average of $\hat{\lambda}_i(t)$ and $\lambda_i(t-1)$, using the hyperparameter α for smoothing. The value α is tuned within a recommended range of $[0.5, 0.9]$ [4].

2.3.4. GradNorm

GradNorm is a PINN training strategy proposed by [7]. Rather than iteratively solving for the loss coefficients, as shown in the previous training strategies, GradNorm seeks to make these coefficients trainable. The model parameters (i.e., weights and biases) remain trainable under the loss expression provided by Equation (4). The general form for the loss expression, \mathcal{L} given the loss scaling parameters, λ , at a training step t , are

$$\mathcal{L}(t; \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^k \left| G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t) - \bar{G}_{\theta}(t) \times [r_i(t)]^{\alpha} \right|_1, \quad (9)$$

where each loss weight $\lambda_i(t)$ is now optimized as training progresses. The definitions for $G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t)$, $\bar{G}_{\theta}(t)$, and $r_i(t)$ are:

$$(a) \quad G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t) = \|\nabla_{\theta} \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i(t)\|_2 \quad (b) \quad \bar{G}_{\theta}(t) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t) \quad (c) \quad r_i(t) = \frac{\mathcal{L}_i(t)}{\mathcal{L}_i(0) \cdot \bar{\mathcal{L}}(t)}. \quad (10)$$

Here $G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t)$ is defined as the gradient norm for each task, i , and is calculated using the L_2 norm of the gradient. Each of the gradients for λ are calculated individually for each task i across all objectives k , where $i \in [1, 2, \dots, k]$ and $\bar{G}_{\theta}(t)$ is averages across all objectives. $r_i(t)$ is defined as the relative inverse training rate for task i ; the term is used to determine the rate at which task i has improved up until timestep t . α is introduced as an additional hyperparameter.

The underlying goal of this difference between actual and target gradient norms is to ensure that $G_{\theta}^{(i)}(t) \approx \bar{G}_{\theta}(t)[r_i(t)]^{\alpha}$; thereby balancing each loss term. Through this, the gradient updating rule

introduces a new hyperparameter, α , which dictates how sensitive the gradient is to $r_i(t)$. A range of $\alpha \in (0, 3)$ is used for hyperparameter tuning as recommended by [7].

2.4. Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Quantification

MCD serves as a frequentist approach to quantifying model uncertainty by using dropout layers in a deep learning model during both training and inference [10]. To perform MCD, dropout layers are enabled during inference – where a random percentage of the models' neurons and their connections are removed from the model, according to the dropout rate – and multiple forward passes are performed on a consistent test dataset. From this, a set of predictions is generated that can be found to approximate a Gaussian distribution, $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$, where a mean μ and the variance, σ^2 , can be sampled from. For the following study, 100 forward passes are performed using a dropout rate of 10% to quantify the model's uncertainty.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each model architecture, PINN, LSTM and PI-LSTM, was trained for 1000 epochs. For comparison, the whole data set required 4 minutes to solve using an ODE solver, while the SoftAdapt algorithm required 4.75 min to train with negligible time afterwards for predictions (using an Intel i7-13700H (2.40 GHz) CPU with 16 Gb 5200 MT/s RAM). A comparison of architectures training and validation loss curves is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. LSTM and PI-LSTM training and validation curves via the MAE.

A sample of the performance of the three architectures on testing and extrapolation samples is shown in Figure 3. The PINN model falls short of both the LSTM and PI-LSTMs, due to its architecture's inability to account for dependence on previous system states for many different operations. Employment of the learning strategies does not address the limitation of PINNs in this application. While the LSTM and PI-LSTM models both exhibit excellent performance on data in the testing domain, the LSTM model generalizes poorly when predicting longer reactor operations, whereas the PI-LSTM is relatively unaffected. The learning strategies discussed in Section 2 will next be applied to the best performing architecture: the PI-LSTM. A quantitative comparison of the LSTM, PINN, and base PI-LSTM is given in Table I.

For each model architecture and PI-LSTM training strategy, Table I lists various performance and error metrics, including the predictive correlation coefficient R^2 , the mean absolute percent error (MAE), the relative root mean square error (rRMSE), the relative maximum error (rME), and the relative uncertainty (RU). Significant performance improvements are observed at only two points: First, in the transition from the PINN towards an LSTM (with no physics loss); and second, when incorporating a physics loss term into the LSTM. The best performing PI-LSTM learning strategy was the SoftAdapt algorithm; however, the gap in performance is minimal. Notably, the other learning strategies appear to increase the error and prediction uncertainties.

Figure 3. Performance of the LSTM, PINN, & PI-LSTM (base) on a testing (left) and extrapolation sample (right).

Table I. Results on accuracy and uncertainty metrics for each model architecture and learning strategy. Note that the four learning strategies are only applied to the PI-LSTM model.

Method	R^2	MAPE (%)	rRMSE (%)	rME (%)	RU (%)
PINN	0.999	2.817	3.861	13.4	0.057
LSTM	0.991	0.393	0.699	6.45	0.078
PI-LSTM (Base)	0.999	0.245	0.337	2.86	0.031
SoftAdapt	0.999	0.204	0.323	2.83	0.031
ReLoBRaLo	0.999	0.264	0.417	4.01	0.066
LRA	0.999	0.522	0.776	4.11	0.068
GradNorm	0.999	0.264	0.409	3.61	0.061

ReLoBRaLo, GradNorm, and Learning Rate Annealing may incur a greater error and uncertainty due to their exclusive objective of balancing all loss terms, while SoftAdapt possesses the ability to favor the best-performing losses by setting the $\beta < 0$. This statement is supported by the optimal value for β found to be approximately -8.971 through the hyperparameter tuning performed. This value for β indicates that SoftAdapt achieves superior performance by providing the most weight to the best-performing loss term, while all other learning strategies simply balance all objectives.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Three model architectures were explored with the task of predicting reactor operations: PINN, LSTM, and PI-LSTM. While the traditional PINN recognizes perturbations in power correctly, the model's predictions are limited by the PINN architecture and cannot accurately model the time-dependent behavior in this application. The LSTM is found to perform well on all accounts; however, the architecture fails to extrapolate predictions for longer operations. The following study finds the PI-LSTM to exhibit superior performance on all accounts by benefiting from a physics-informed loss and long/short-term memory of patterns within the temporal reactor operations data. When the dynamic nature of reactor operations is considered, the results conclude that the PI-LSTM architecture is the best for predicting reactor operations it has not seen, and should be further investigated on more complex reactor models and operations datasets.

The learning strategies, SoftAdapt, ReLoBRaLo, LRA, and GradNorm were implemented into a PI-LSTM architecture for the example reactor kinetics problem. Compared to the base PI-LSTM, the various learning strategies did not offer significant improvement, and at times reduced performance. The lack of significant gains in performance may be attributed to two potential factors: The simplicity of the problem leading to high accuracy without complicated techniques, and the objective the strategies were applied to. The PI-LSTM performed significantly well on the training, validation, test, and gener-

alization sets. Therefore, expected gains through the learning strategies would be limited, and potential additional variance due to the changing loss weights may have led to more inconsistent training and potentially poorer performance within the tight margins.

Future work seeks to address the impact of noise, inaccurate or uncertain physics parameters, or incomplete physics on the performance the PI-LSTM and its learning strategies. The inclusion of incomplete physics or physics parameters within the loss function may serve as a disadvantage to a physics-informed architecture. While this presents an issue that may be addressed through the learning strategies described above, the solution presents an additional opportunity. Another possible avenue for future work is applying the model to detect nuclear proliferation and other anomalous scenarios dynamically. The proposed PI-LSTM serves as a fitting model for capturing these anomalies, as it can predict reactor operations solely based on control-element data (or reactivity perturbations).

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